

SYPHILIS DISEASE AND DIAGNOSIS

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Abstract. Syphilis or wound disease is a sexually transmitted disease that can cause serious complications if left untreated, but can be easily treated with the right approach. The causative agent is the bacterium *Treponema pallidum*[1,2,3]. The disease is divided into stages (primary, secondary, hidden and tertiary). Each stage of the disease has its own different symptoms.

Key words: syphilis, lymphadenitis, pneumonia, chancre, population, serological, reaction

INTRODUCTION

Wound disease is also one of the dermatological diseases. The wound disease called syphilis is an infectious venereal disease caused by a leaky *treponema* (spirochete) infection. This microorganism is called leaching because it stains poorly with aniline dye. The disease is sexually transmitted through the skin and mucous membranes. It can also be transmitted through direct contact and various types of household items.

Syphilis is the most dangerous infectious disease. It can be transmitted very easily, and there are several routes of transmission[4,5,6]. According to medical statistics, the wound is transmitted in 95% of cases through sexual intercourse and in 5% of cases through daily contacts or infected blood. In addition, it can be transmitted through the placenta from mother to child and through blood transfusions. In the first stage, the wound disease is transmitted only through infected blood.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Material collection technique and microscopic diagnosis. Laboratory diagnosis of the wound includes two methods: microscopic and serological examination methods. In the first stage of the disease, tissue fluid and lymph node points taken from solid chancre (primary syphiloma), in the second stage from eroded papules and cerbar warts[7,8]. The obtained tissue fluid is checked. In primary syphilis, reading *treponemas* are more concentrated in the spaces between connective tissue fibers, on the periphery of the damaged area, around lymphatic and blood vessels. *interstitial mites* are located in the oral cavity. It is very difficult to find them microscopically in tertiary lesions. Because they decrease in damaged areas of the skin.

When taking material from a wound, the surface of a hard chancre, erosion, papule, serbar condyloma is first thoroughly wiped with cotton or gauze tampon soaked in physiological solution[9,10], and then cleaned with dry cotton. If the wound is covered with a black crust, then it is moistened and then carefully removed. Sometimes it is recommended to soak it with a physical solution for several hours. There are several ways to extract tissue fluid from a hard chancre.

A method of squeezing tissue fluid. This method is the most convenient for the laboratory technician among other methods. The laboratory technician (or the patient himself) begins to slowly squeeze the two edges of the wound with the left hand using the head and index fingers or with tweezers[11,12,13]. Without rubber gloves, it is not appropriate to touch the wound, erosion, serbar candlestick with your fingers. During compression, if you stop for a few seconds and then squeeze again like a massage, the tissue fluid will be better released. The leakage of tissue fluid, which contains a lot of blood, makes it difficult to find treponemas.

Tissue fluid is usually obtained by touching the edge of a cover glass to the edge of the wound[14,15,16,17]. The fluid from the entire wound site contains a large number of treponemas.

Scratch method. Although this method is rarely used compared to the squeeze method, it sometimes gives good results. It is convenient to use this method of scratching to remove tissue fluid from erosions on the cervix, oral cavity, cervical warts. First, the wound, the surface of the erosion is thoroughly wiped with a physiological solution, gently wiped on one side for 20-30 seconds with a sterile scalpel, tweezers or the edge of a glass. After 40-60 seconds, tissue fluid will start to glisten from the scratched area[18,19]. Tissue fluid should not be taken outside of the laboratory, as the fluid will dry out immediately, and it will be dangerous to others because it is infectious.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

Obtaining tissue fluid from erosive papules in the oral cavity in a secondary recurrent lesion or from a hard chancre located on the tongue, palate, and tonsils in a primary lesion is an important requirement for the laboratory worker[20,21]. In this case, depending on the location of the eroded papule or wound, both methods of obtaining material can be used. Separated tissue fluid should be sucked in a Pasteur pipette with a rubber balloon (suction method).

Burning or Izhevsky method. In this case, the surface of the examined morphological elements is burned with heated platinum, as a result, a bubble is

found at the place of burning. The fluid taken from the blister is examined in a dark viewing area. All used medical instruments are sterilized in an autoclave by soaking them in a disinfectant for several hours. It is forbidden to store these instruments in a mixed state with other laboratory instruments. As soon as the rubber bags are opened, they are placed in a 1:1000 diluted sulema solution, and then thrown away.

A darkened field of view is the most convenient way to see live treponema. Romanovsky Gimza, Zimin, Burri recommended the staining examination of treponemas. The disadvantage of these methods is that the laboratory technician does not see treponemas while they are alive. The rate of finding treponemas in drugs is 7-10%, which is also evidence of a flaw in the method.

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